

Supplementary Material:
Interview with Clinical Expert

Transcript of an expert interview with Hannes Gieseler, physician and research fellow at the Institute of Sexology and Sexual Medicine, Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin. The interview was conducted by Vera Czehmann on October 13, 2025, in the context of the VERANDA project¹, and includes expert reflections on preventive clinical practice, anonymization, annotation guideline development, and the interpretation of pilot findings. The transcript was edited for readability; disfluencies, repetitions, and obvious transcription errors were corrected.

Thank you so much for taking the time to sit down with me and talk about our work. First, could you tell me a little bit about your professional background and your current work in this area?

HG: My professional background is a very interesting story, because I actually started by studying design, then I was making documentary films, and then I went into medicine. I studied medicine, and after I became a doctor, a physician, I worked at the Institute of Sexology and Sexual Medicine at Charité in Berlin and worked in the prevention project *Dunkelfeld* for many years. So this is about 11 years now.

The prevention project that you mentioned is preventive work with individuals concerned about their CSAM use. I think we need to clarify first that CSAM in our context is child sexual abuse material. The clients that you worked with, and still work with, are individuals with self-reported concern about their use of such materials. Is that correct?

HG: Yes, most of them, even. We have to differentiate between the digital or online project, which offers remote treatment, and the original prevention project, which is also known as *Kein Täter werden*, which used to be an in-person treatment only, for people with pedophilia. This used to be, and still is, an inclusion criterion in the original in-person prevention project and intervention, because we are actually doing secondary prevention of, let's say, not transforming the fantasies into behavior. The behavior would be, on the one hand, child sexual abuse, CSA, and on the other hand, which we see more often now, CSAM use. So child sexual abuse material is just very easily accessible, unfortunately, on the internet. And therefore, almost any person with a sexual interest in children is using this material. And this is illegal, it's harming children. It's harming the individuals themselves, even. And many of them want to stop. And we support them, on the one hand, in person, if regionally available, and then also in the digital and online spaces. We have one remote video treatment project, and another one is *Troubled Desire*, which was originally a self-help platform. So we had modules and a self-test, and we extended the set of modules by chat interventions. So we are currently running the second chat study, which takes this approach. We have a lot of clinical experience, actually, the original prevention project is now 20 years old. And like five years ago, we started the online project, and we used the same approach we're using in person. We just modified it a bit for chatting, to make it shorter, because we don't have as much time as we would have in talking to them for like a year. So we have very condensed treatment plan manuals, just four sessions, 50 minutes each, as in usual psychotherapy. A specific intervention just to stop CSAM use. It's not addressing offline offenders, they are excluded from the program,

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but it's meant specifically to stop CSAM use. So that's what we are doing in *Troubled Desire* in the second iteration of the study now.

You just differentiated between CSAM use and CSA and, before we move into annotation, I would like to ask how you understand the clinical landscape of this, specifically, how do you clinically distinguish between pedophilic disorder and CSAM-related behavior? Do they necessarily go hand in hand with each other, are there important distinctions to make?

HG: Let's say the major difference is fantasy is not behavior. So anything that happens in your mind, just thoughts and fantasies, is absolutely fine. Your thoughts are completely free. You can have any kind of fantasy, it's absolutely fine. There's nothing bad about it. It's even good to have it and not to suppress and avoid it. But this is a risk factor to, on the one hand, develop pedophilic disorder, according to the clinical diagnostic criteria. So the two biggest manuals in the world, there's the ICD and the DSM. And their criteria differ a bit, but they are basically the same. So if the sexual urges or the sexual fantasies towards children are not just once, and they are persistent for, let's say, six months, and they come with either suffering or problematic behavior because, again, the fantasies or the pedophilic disorder is a risk factor for child sexual abuse and for the use of child sexual abuse material as well. But that's the major distinction. And the behavior, which is CSA or use of CSAM, that's what we consider the problematic behavior. It's harming, it's illegal. And this is, it's the worst thing. Touching a child sexually is, from a societal point of view, the worst thing you can do. And that kind of takes us back to the fantasies and to pedophilia. If you just have fantasies or you're suffering from the fantasies, but you don't do anything, you are still stigmatized because it's automatically, in our minds, somehow related to behavior. And that's why it's so important to distinguish between the fantasy, the possible disorder, the suffering, and the behavioral part. That's what we treat, we treat the behavioral part, and the suffering, of course. So we try to achieve well-being, but we don't treat the fantasies. The fantasies are free, and fine. So it's hard to distinguish.

You actually made a segue to the next topic I wanted to ask you about, what misconceptions or stigmas about the sexual preference or pedophilic disorder do you often encounter either from the public or maybe even within professional circles?

HG: There has been a survey on this, where I believe they asked people on the street, which has become famous for doing this research on stigmatization of people with pedophilia. There's still a huge societal stigmatization. So most of them don't want to see them as friends, or they want to have them in jail, or even dead, although they haven't done anything, just in response to the hypothetical question of what would you do with a person with sexual fantasies towards children? So that's really a threat. I mean, it's really a threat to people having these fantasies and having a problem with it, and maybe even having already used CSAM. I would think it's one of the hardest things for them to open up about. And again, it's the relation, because everyone thinks of behavior in connection to pedophilia. That's why it's so stigmatized.

Building on that, how do you feel, from your personal experience, those misconceptions affect both disclosure and also engagement in therapy?

HG: I mean, the hardest thing is to overcome the barrier and to speak about it. But probably a lot of people with pedophilia or let's say with fantasies, sexual fantasies, too many of them, are not even self-aware or not

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doing anything about it. But this is the population we don't see in the clinic. We don't see them in research because it's not necessary for them to open up. But if they suffer, they of course search for help, and yes, they always fear being judged because of their thoughts. They always fear being reported to authorities. It's not that bad in Germany because we don't have mandatory reporting, we have doctor-patient confidentiality, so they can tell us everything in the clinical setting. But many of the people who came forward to the in-person treatment project told us it was the worst thing ever, just calling, making the appointment. And then, again, going there, stepping through the door, and sitting in the room with a therapist and talking about the fantasies, whether it's the first time or not. And this is probably one of the biggest challenges to overcome these barriers.

Do you feel that the availability of online interventions has kind of lowered the barriers?

HG: Yeah, absolutely. This is maybe even the major achievement, or the on top achievement, because it is, or at least it feels, much more anonymous. I mean, we guarantee them that they don't need to tell us names or email addresses, so by design we keep it as private as possible. But it can still happen that they share some personal details. But for many of them, it's much easier to write something in a text message than calling someone. And it just feels much more comfortable, much safer, for a lot of people. It's really, really great to overcome this barrier because many people just wouldn't come to an in-person treatment.

Do you think that the perceived difference in anonymity and safety is bigger than the actual difference between online intervention and in-person intervention? I'm wondering because you touched on information that even if they don't disclose, for example, their names, they address other personally identifying information and there might still be information retained in the chats that we end up working with, that could identify them.

HG: There's at least some digital traces. It's actually saved on servers, so we keep the data. This is one aspect. The aspect of the in-person treatment or remote video treatment is that we see them, at least a certain number of people do. So the therapeutic team sees their faces and hears their voices. So they would be able to recognize them. This is a dimension or quality that doesn't happen in text-message-based chat. So it's two different aspects. One is more a digital trace, the other one – at the beginning of the in-person treatment project, clients were coming in with hats and dark sunglasses just to not be discovered.

Understandable, from what you described earlier.

HG: Yeah, absolutely.

So in the work we do, we work with chat transcripts from interventions done within your chat study. What are the goals of VERANDA, the project we both work on, regarding these interventions, regarding privacy and anonymization of this highly sensitive data?

HG: From my perspective, the goal of the VERANDA project is kind of to ensure the safety of our way of anonymization and even improve the anonymization. That's one big thing. And additionally, what we're also developing is video and audio anonymization, which is not used in a real scenario yet. As of now, we are using the chat in a real scenario. They're real people, and they are really looking for help. And one goal is to have the opportunity to do video- and audio-based interventions as well, and to have them be safe and

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anonymous. So that's one thing. The other thing is also to make sure that the chats are really anonymous. And then on top of this, based on the anonymous or anonymized chats, we want to see if we can still derive the information to do a relapse prediction for potential CSAM use relapse, which is actually super fancy, to do anonymization and then relapse prediction, because neither of these have been done before, using machine learning models to do this and to help us with the two tasks.

Adding to what you said, and this is also something we consider in the risk assessment annotation work that we did, is that in order to publish any data in a corpus, it is of utmost importance to make sure that the data is completely anonymous, not just de-identified, meaning that, any personally identifying information, for example, also so called indirect identifiers are removed. I would like to move on to the annotation work that we did. I want to ask, when we initially developed the guidelines, what clinical considerations were most important for you?

HG: For the development, my process was that I went through chats that I did or someone else did, and marked sections where I had the feeling, okay, this I would focus on, toward risk or protection. So either the client says something that gives me an indication that they're protected from using CSAM, or an indication of, oh, they're at risk. This is usually an implication for me to do something about it as a therapist. If something indicates risk, then I would always address the risk. And this is of course done by language. And it's kind of the same process in the in-person treatment. Something that I learned during my ten years of treating people in person, just doing first interviews with them, leading groups with them, doing individual therapy with them, giving them medication, we were always sitting together, at least once a week, in a team and discussing all the patients, especially the risk cases. We would also talk about why we see the risk. So from a therapeutic perspective, risk is always the major target. What we do is we want to try to address the dynamic risk factors, risk factors we can influence, like coping for example. We also have the forensic risk assessment tools in the back of our mind that influenced this work in the beginning, such as Static, Stable, Acute, and we also use the Therapist Rating Scale with in-person patients. We have done this, every three or six months, sitting together, two therapists, and then doing a consensus rating of how we would see the risk. This is kind of ingrained in me and in how I would see this, and I tried to translate this from the transcript again into a manual for annotation. So that's probably how it worked.

You mentioned, and I would like for you to elaborate on that, you made the difference between forensic and clinical populations. I think it's super important to talk about this, and why the tools developed for forensic populations and contact offenses are not directly transferable to the work that we do.

HG: There are different factors. The forensic samples, people who are in prison for child sexual abuse, are the ones where most of the risk tools are developed, because that's the available sample of people. They are at higher risk and that's why they were detected by the police. And then there's a huge field of undetected CSAM, let's say, I'm estimating, about 80% of CSAM is undetected, and they're never in contact with the legal authorities. And there must be a reason. This is also something we see in our in-person sample, we always try to see how we can influence the risk factors. There were some alterations during the treatment, but not as many as expected. So the assumption is that the sample is different. And, once again, different between CSA offenders, who the most risk tools are developed for, detected CSAM offenders, and undetected CSAM offenders who just come forward because they are suffering and they see this is harming them and they want to stop. So we don't know actually what it is exactly, but they are different. This is maybe a good story that

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reflects it: a police officer told us, “we are catching just the stupid ones.” And, I mean, this is touching something true. If they know how to protect themselves from detection, it needs a bit of technical skill, just not that much. But a bit.

This really also speaks to the estimate of undetected offenses you made earlier, because I read, and please correct me if I remember this wrongly, but I read that there have been studies on different characteristics between the forensic population of detected CSAM offenders and undetected ones and they indicate that the latter might have a higher level of education in many cases than the previous group, which would really make it easier for them to not be detected.

HG: This is probably a sample from in-person psychotherapy. People who seek psychotherapy are usually higher educated, because there are some biases still. But still, I would always say that there is something about the undetected sample that's definitely different. There's not that much about risk to use CSAM. There's something like the CPORT (Child Pornography Offender Risk Tool), which is really not applicable to a non-forensic sample because a part of the risk estimation is the count of how many times the person has been convicted.

I believe also within the prevention project *Dunkelfeld*, it has been found that the CPORT, on the population that they investigated, which was help seeking individuals, actually had no indicative value for whether or not they had a relapse. Before we move into the annotation discussion, could we define, in our work, what do we consider a risk factor? What do we consider a protective factor, and what do we consider a relapse, which in the forensic field is recidivism, but we need to differentiate between the two.

HG: Yeah. In forensic settings, it's a detection, and there's usually an index offense. Even if they get therapy, in forensic settings, they of course would just talk about the index offense. If there's more, they wouldn't talk about it. That's why we are excluding the people who are detected. If they are self-referred, if they are coming forward to get treatment without detection, we would address the relapse directly, and they don't get judged for it. Sometimes it's difficult and especially if they are in groups, there could be, of course, judgment from other group members. But in chat, for example, it's really easy to not judge them for the relapse, for another offense, another event of using CSAM, but we will address it, and we talk about what happened to get to know the pattern that's behind it. And that's basically also how the therapy works.

For the annotation scheme, how did you decide which factors to code as protective versus risk factors? Or what's the meaning behind these names, that you gave this group of factors that you're looking at?

HG: Well, there's a very interesting model we started to use, which is looking at this like a continuous spectrum of one factor or one dimension. And you could move towards risk or you could move towards protection. So a very good example is always trustful relationships, intimacy. If you have fulfilled, trustful relationships and fulfilled intimacy, it's obviously kind of protecting you from using abuse material or abusing someone, whether it's a child or an adult. And if you don't have that intimacy, then it's like something is lacking, and then you get into the risk of using material, or relapsing.

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In the pilot annotation that we did and in the iterative annotation meetings and discussions with the other team members, which factors or which concepts of factors or topics did you feel were most ambiguous or debated in the team?

HG: Probably the functional versus dysfunctional coping. But maybe because this is kind of the heart of everything. So it is kind of always about regulation of emotions. The dysfunctional behavior is somehow always related to the regulation of emotions you probably don't want to have. So this, I feel, has been annotated a lot because we of course talk about it a lot in the sessions. And there is that twist about it, that you need to reflect on the dysfunctional behavior. And this is, of course, reflected in the language, in what you say. But a reflection of the dysfunctional behavior could be protective. And that's why this is sometimes clashing and not easy to distinguish between. Is this still just talking about it, or is it consciously reflecting how my pattern works, and therefore again protective, because I know when I'm in a bad mood, then I will tend to do stupid things.

These were actually the biggest confusion hubs in the first iterations of annotations between protective and risk factors in the domain of coping. Do you believe that the relatively high disagreement between annotators within these factors stems mostly from problems like boundary drift, like annotators aren't sure which span exactly to annotate or could there be there some genuine clinical ambiguity to be found there, meaning that, even if we have disagreements on some of these factors, they're not inherently wrong?

HG: Yeah. I mean, that's the effect we had quite often, that the same thing was once annotated as risk and once as protective. And this relates to the model of the continuum that it's going from risk to protective and you can use it like a slider. So as I said before, there's always this consciousness towards that if it's a conscious reflection of dysfunctional coping, then it can be misread as risk, although it's protective. So that's my major theory on how the critical disagreements happen.

Do you remember any other categories that you can think of that this continuum model applies to?

HG: In the sense that it could be misread?

Yeah.

HG: Just an example that we used, we tend to classify relationships, any relationship, as good, and sometimes they are not. Just to say, "I'm in a relationship," doesn't help anybody. And if there's no additional information about the quality of the relationship, we really don't know if this is a protective or risk factor.

And in what ways, in the annotation scheme and the guidelines, did we make it clear how to make these distinctions?

HG: Yeah, I think at some point we added, for example, the quality of the relationship. I think we didn't do that enough yet for the coping factor, but it should work quite well for the relationship spectrum.

I was going to ask, actually, which kinds of disagreements you think make sense clinically, but I feel we talked about this.

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HG: There's another one, though, which is the factor past problematic behavior or past CSAM behavior. It's also sometimes misleading because it's not really clear if it's, again, just a reflection of something that happened years ago and how that went. I sometimes struggle a bit with it, but I know there's an impact and I think there were some results on this in the analysis. And, you know, this is what's a bit tricky. I would really like to kick that one out because I have no idea how to classify it correctly.

It's also one of the very few factors that we consider that are not dynamic, actually, it's static.

HG: Yeah, and it's actually, somehow, also the overarching target factor. So maybe it shouldn't be annotated as a risk factor when we talk about past CSAM behavior. That's more the condition we target in treatments to go to zero, we probably shouldn't use as a risk factor. This is the idea I have.

On what we call critical disagreements, the same span annotated as both protective and risk factor, how would clinicians normally resolve such ambiguities in live sessions?

HG: The short answer is consensus rating, weighted by two therapists, not just by one, because there are always disagreements. And that's why it's usually better to have a separate opinion or a second eye on it. That's how it is usually solved in treatment.

Next, I would like to present to you some results from analyses done on the results of the pilot annotation. I'd like to first share with you something that I call protective ratio, where I examined changes in the relative distribution of protective versus risk factors across sessions. And what this taught me is that there is a significantly positive effect of the session number on this protective ratio, meaning that at least when looked at through the lens of our annotation results, the interventions are trending towards a more positive outcome. Is that something that you also observe clinically?

HG: Yeah, definitely. It doesn't surprise me at all. I mean, we are currently under publication of the effectiveness results, just like the first study. And it showed effectiveness of the intervention. So this is a really cool reflection of what we actually did, that the risk is going down and the protective factors are going up. This is exactly what we address with the intervention, and obviously it works. So yeah, it's great, but it's not surprising.

I actually was worried that we would have a different outcome for this, by the way. I was entirely unsure how it would go. Very glad to know this. We also plotted in a graph the means of protective versus risk factors, per client over time. So, on one axis, it shows like session one, two, three, four, and on the other axis it shows the total number of our annotated risk versus protective factors. And what we're seeing is that it actually starts with risk factors being higher than protective factors. And then towards the end of the intervention, that flipped. We also had two annotators separately label each session with a label for relapse, meaning, in our context, CSAM use. So what I did is I tried to find out whether the protective ratio, or the number of risk or protective factors changed around reported relapse events. For this, I assigned what we call windows, so a window for pre-relapse, $t - 1$, this is the session before the relapse happened, since they happened between sessions, and then $t + 1$ for the session directly following the relapse, and then contrasted them against all other sessions from the same clients, which I used as a baseline. For the protective ratio,

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pre-relapse it decreased relative to the baseline, meaning the protective ratio was lower pre-relapse. And then, it also decreased after these relapse events despite the trend of going upwards over time. We also found out that sessions immediately surrounding relapse contain higher rates of risk factors before the relapse and then after the relapse, lower rates of protective factors. Is this something that aligns with your clinical experience?

HG: Did you take into consideration if the client relapsed again after the session?

We did not, actually. This totally could be done in a further analysis step, but for the very small sample we have from the pilot annotation, I haven't done this.

HG: I wondered about that, because I wonder if that has an impact when the pre-relapse session is a post-relapse session as well. So if it's both. But other than that, from a logic point of view, it seems to make sense for the pre-relapse session. I mean, in the best case, that's the one we look at for prediction. Although it's a very small sample yet, it seems to, at least, show some direction, some indication of relapse prediction. The session after relapse, this is a bit complicated because we are still using the relapse itself as a factor, and that's always in the annotation. And we also look at the intervention itself. So the manual says if there was a relapse, address the relapse. So we would talk about the relapse a lot in the session after the relapse. We would also talk about dysfunctional coping mechanisms etc., we would address all the risk factors. So they might be more prevalent in the post-relapse session because we would actually be interested, and the manual says to talk about it.

You're touching on something we discussed during the guideline development as well, I believe before the second iteration – we added a label for relapse behavior since the last session that exists outside of the risk and protective factors, to make sure that this current behavior, the target factor, is not included in our risk estimation.

HG: We are, though, still annotating past problematic behavior as a risk factor. So for example, when you're talking about a repeating relapse pattern, you would mention earlier CSAM behavior as well, in addition to the recent relapse behavior.

I see your point. So this means the higher prevalence of past problematic behavior in post-relapse sessions should not automatically be read as a direct signal of a preceding relapse but rather earlier problematic behavior also being more likely to come up in the therapeutic processing of the relapse. We also did analyses on the exact factor level, so not only talking about the risk versus protective level, but the exact factors. Unfortunately, none of these were statistically significant, at least, with this approach. In the future, of course, I would like to change the approach, but since we're working on the pilot set for now, this is what made sense. We quantified these relapse-aligned changes, as I call them, using two different lenses. So on the one hand, I looked at presence as a binary label. Just, was the factor present in a pre- or post-session or not. And then also a normalized rate, which is the factor counts divided by the total annotations in the respective sessions. I did both because the rates can also indicate the relative dominance of these codes just before, or after relapse rather than just looking at was it present or not. And for pre-relapse sessions, across both lenses, the strongest changes were increases for mentions of risk factor three, avoidance, suppression and missing acceptance of the sexual preference, and also for risk factor seven, which was comorbidities, low well-being and other psychological problems or diseases.

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HG: And changes, again, changes means what?

Changes for these factors mean they increased in pre-relapse sessions. And then on the other side, we had smaller decreases across several protective factors such as healthy intimacy or recognition and functional handling of impulses, and also well-being and therapist's affirmation of commitment. So the protective factors that I just mentioned, they went down in pre-relapse sessions. I'm wondering, are there factors that you might have expected to be either increased or decreased in these pre-relapse sessions, from your experience?

HG: So as you have also experienced, the clients are a bit individual in terms of one has more of this risk factor, the other one has more of this. The same is true for protective factors. So I would not expect to have changes in one risk factor or one protective factor before relapse for all clients. But just as a pattern, usually some of the protective go down, risk goes up, and then there's the relapse. It doesn't actually matter which one, at least that's the idea of how it should work, that they are kind of equal.

So interestingly enough I did analyses both within factor, within client. So, looking at these factors only within the sessions of one client that had a relapse, and then I also, did an across client sensitivity analysis, and that actually yielded similar rankings.

HG: I mean, it would be, of course, great if we could isolate just the two factors that are always going down, or always changing, before relapse. And it would be just a great situation for relapse prediction. But I doubt that we have enough people in the pilot yet to do it.

Yeah, not yet. This is why I keep saying things like exemplary and descriptively. So then for post relapse sessions, some protective factors decrease in their presence, for example therapy and change commitment, hypersexuality and sexual preoccupation, skills to satisfy sexual needs in a healthy way without harming themselves or others, cooperation with the therapist, healthy sexual behavior and recognition of the abuse of children in the material. These all go down post relapse in client talk. And also, recognition and functional handling of impulses and functional coping strategies. This is across the presence. And then, on the rate side, so over all clients that have relapses, the risk factors avoidance, non-acceptance and unhealthy coping increase.

HG: Yeah, this kind of makes sense, because the unhealthy coping mechanisms are discussed and, post relapse, they are more in the avoidance and non acceptance mode regarding their sexual preference, because again, sexual preference led to a problematic behavior. And this makes it harder to accept it.

Lastly, I would like to talk a little bit about possible clinical support through tools. This is quite long term, but a goal that we have in mind when developing this annotation scheme and guidelines. Are there any patterns in this client talk that you believe rely on clinical intuition, that an AI tool would be very unlikely to capture?

HG: No, I don't think so. It's all based on written text, and there's no facial expression or something you'd need to take into consideration, and that makes it easier. On the other hand, this is tough to say because this is beyond my knowledge of AI, whether it is able to get this ambiguity you have sometimes in there. So, like we mentioned before, our major concern is coping mechanisms. And I'm not sure if an AI is able to get the

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consciousness of that being mentioned versus the thing mentioned itself. And it's even hard for us to differentiate. So I'm not sure at this point. But in general, I think with a big enough data set, it should definitely work to predict, or at least, let's say, to detect an increased risk, which is something that would be really good, just to put more focus on interventions and for the clients to make them conscious that maybe currently they are at higher risk, just to be more aware in the moment.

So this is something that you think would help, if you imagine a supportive tool for therapists, to be able to track, possibly in real time, the, increased risks?

HG: Yeah, absolutely. So the whole idea is inspired by risk prediction for diabetes patients that does something like the diabetic coma, which is a high-risk situation for someone with diabetes. There's a lot of additional clinic costs if patients go into a diabetic coma. And there are AI tools that actually help clinicians to predict when patients could get into a risk situation. And it's the same thing here. If we can do this for CSAM, it would help to reduce a lot of following “costs” in terms of victimization.

Yeah. I was going to add, following “costs”, not in the financial sense, but considering prevention.

HG: Absolutely.

Looking back at the guideline development, the annotation work, what do you find most valuable or most concerning?

HG: Most concerning is that it's a lot of work, it really is. Having done it myself, having humans annotate thousands of things, it's really a pile of work. And most valuable is that it seems to make sense. And that there are some indications, even with the small sample we have now in the pilot, that it could predict relapse. We see changes, and we just need to invest more into which changes of the factors are relevant.

And just because some people, some team members do not have experience with this domain at all, what would you like researchers and developers to better understand about preventive clinical practice?

HG: Oh, this reminds me of the COVID pandemic, and what a colleague said about prevention. There's no glory in prevention. But there is glory in prevention. I mean, it's just the other side of glory.

These are great last words. Thank you so much for taking the time for this.

HG: Thank you for all your work, and your deep dive into the topic, and your interest.